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*Sven-Olof Yrjö Collin***A CRITIQUE OF THE IDEOLOGY OF SUSTAINABILITY
AMONG ACADEMICS AND UNIVERSITIES**

Sustainability has turned into an ideology, promoted by commercial and political organizations, but now also by academics and their universities. Here I discuss sustainability as a conservative ideology, that through activist actions by academics and universities refute the academic ground of academic freedom. Through anecdotal examples from my own academic subject, business administration, I notice that it has ideological elements and that it has elements that are in accordance to sustainability. I end by a call for academics to not be political agents, so called activists, but to perform their academic duty, to critically study reality and to give scientific knowledge to society, in order to make society better able to perform sustainable actions.

Key words: academic freedom, activism, business administration, ideology objectivity, sustainability.

Коллін Свен-Олоф. Критика ідеології сталого розвитку в академічних колах та в університетах.

У статті критично розглядається концепція сталого розвитку, яка з ідеології комерційних та політичних організацій, перетворилася на ідеологію, яку підтримують науковці та університети. Автор привертає увагу на історичний зсув від марксистського активізму в 1960-х і 1970-х роках до сучасного переходу до сталого розвитку, наголошуючи на його консервативному характері, який протирічить основам академічної свободи. Такі програми ООН, як *Цілі сталого розвитку 2030 (Agenda 2030)* і *Принципи відповідальної управлінської освіти (PRME)*, інтегрують сталий розвиток в університетські навчальні програми, що сприяє відтворенню ідеологій, якими керує ООН. У критиці консервативної орієнтації сталого розвитку, автор порівнює її з доктринами стримування, а не прогресу, заперечуючи припущення про вирівнювання погреб між поколіннями. Стверджується, що університети, які приймають концепцію сталості, часто ризикують стати розповсюджувачами ідеології, що не відповідає основній місії університетів, а саме: місії неупередженого генерування знань. Втім, автор визнає, що деякі дисципліни, наприклад, бізнес адміністрування, частково спираються на ідеологічні поняття та елементи сталого розвитку. Стаття закінчується закликом автора до

академічної свободи. Університети повинні зосередитися на критичних дослідженнях, в академічних колах має панувати нейтралітет та професіоналізм для надання об'єктивних знань, а науковці повинні бути не політичними агентами, так званими активістами, а виконувати свій академічний обов'язок, критично досліджувати реальність і надавати наукові знання суспільству, щоб зробити його більш здатним до постійного та стійкого розвитку.

Ключові слова: академічна свобода, бізнес-адміністрування, ідеологія, об'єктивність, політична активність, сталий розвиток.

The political activism at the university

«Every academic, researcher or teacher, has to declare his or hers position in the class struggle».

That was a statement made by a professor in sociology during the 70'ies in Sweden. For him, the universities were part of the class struggle, and was therefore an actor that could support or hinder the development towards the happy communist society. I reacted negatively to that statement. Even if I was then the chair of the local youth democratic socialist party, and I had been convinced by Myrdal (1969) that economics contained hidden values, I thought that in academia I want scientific knowledge that is not political in its content, but could have political effects, but without me as an academic promoting the effects through political action. Politics and scientific knowledge should be as separate as possible, even if it is true that academia is drawn into the class struggle and there become a part of the class struggle, and even if it is true that researchers use values when selecting research subject. But that political process is partly because academia is weak and not totally occupied by the scientist ethos, to find the scientific knowledge, whatever it is, whatever the consequences are, whatever societal interest that is promoted or hindered by the knowledge.

The communists at the universities in the 60'ies and 70'ies never succeeded in transforming the universities to become active actors in the class struggle. Their push toward university activism faded away. By then I performed my research career by investigating the power structures of the capitalist organization, the corporation, under the concept of 'corporate governance'. While the selection of the subject was guided by my socialist

interest in social power structures and processes, I have mostly used, not as expected, the theory of Marxism, but mainly the bourgeois theories of agency theory and institutional theory.

At the end of my career, from about 2015 and onwards, the political activist professor has, however, returned. But now the class struggle has been replaced by sustainability. The radical, progressive modernist movement towards the utopia of eternal peace in society through communism is now replaced by a conservative movement towards the utopia of eternal peace with the nature through sustainability.

An international political organization, UN, that started as a peace organization, have created a political program for sustainability, termed Agenda 2030. It contains, among other things, PRME, which is an initiative directed towards business schools and universities. It offers the opportunity for those institutions that have programs in business studies to integrate Agenda 2030 in its education. There exists universities and business schools today that have accepted PRME and integrated the UN agenda in their programmes and teaching. In this way these institutions, supposedly academic, do take a political stand and are promoting a specific ideology, sustainability, and how it is interpreted by the political organization UN. That is to say that universities are active in promoting and reproducing the ideology of sustainability according to UN.

Indeed, it is a paradox to experience the conservative political action of sustainability performed by university professors, when realizing that it implies the implementation of the last of the eleven theses from Karl Marx text «Theses On Feuerbach» from 1845:

«Philosophers have hitherto only interpreted the world in various ways; the point is to change it».

In this paper I will present a critique of sustainability and of university activism promoting the ideology and the political action of sustainability. I will show that my subject, business administration, is by no means free from ideology promotion but that it also contains ideas of sustainability. The paper ends with a call for letting the professors and universities produce knowledge and letting society using this knowledge in order to produce political action. By that call that I oppose the eleven thesis by Marx and I refuse to follow the imperative of the sociology professor, to being forced

to state my political position, though I will do it voluntary, in order to be able to perform my argumentation.

A definition and a critique of sustainability

Sustainability is a term that connote a very nebulous concept [16] and is, at best, «a pluralistic paradigm» [19], despite the fact that research, with its natural demand of clear and precise definitions of concepts, has developed exponentially in published research since about 2010 [23]. In fact, Bonevac (2010) claim that it is easy to show that many definitions of sustainability are even absurd. But the nebulous concept could also be its strength, especially when it concerns sustainability. If we had a very concise, well-defined concept, it would very clearly include certain phenomena's and exclude others. Since our overall knowledge of, for example consequences on nature and humans, are very small relative to the actual consequences, we have a large uncertainty in understanding consequences. If we, by a nebulous concept, study issues that by a very precise definition would exclude some consequences of the issue, we would not find consequences that a more loosely defined concept would be able to find. So, the uncertainty in our knowledge makes it almost adequate to have a nebulous definition of sustainability, since nebulous is what our knowledge is. On the third hand, a nebulous concept opens for endless fights about definitions, which will consume a lot of researcher's energy, which hardly will fulfil any criteria of sustainability. And, not the least, with bad nebulous definitions we run probably higher risk of having concepts that contains hidden values.

Sustainability is not only a concept but has evolved into a kind of an ideology. By ideology I mean concepts and theories that declare what is, but that also contains normative statements of what should be and supports specific groups of society, typically through legitimizing them and their actions. Sustainability as an ideology contains the norm that every generation has to act in a manner that do not limit the choices of the next generation.

This norm is found in the classical definition of sustainability made by the Brundtland commission: «*Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs*» [4, p. 24].

It says that today should not compromise the future ability. This sounds like Robert Crawley, 7th Earl of Grantham, in the famous TV-series, *Downton Abbey*, when he says to his daughter: «*My fortune is the work of others who laboured to build a great dynasty. Do I have the right to destroy their work or impoverish that dynasty? I am a custodian, my dear, not an owner. I must strive to be worthy of the task I've been set*». Notice that it is the Earl, a conservative person in outlook and action, that declares the sustainability of the dynasty.

Sustainability has been developed into a whole system of thoughts, where sustainability has been divided into economic, social and environmental dimensions [23]. This conception, and variants of it, has today characteristics of being an established system of thoughts, declaring what is and what should be, and by doing so, is able to guide both human understanding and human action. Thus, it has turned into an ideology. Indeed, it has been claimed to be a «<...> *robust, alternative world view to the industrial, neoliberal paradigm*» [19].

It is sometimes claimed that sustainability is not a perspective and not an ideology, but a necessity [9]. Thus, it is an ideology that, according to the concept of Gramsci [13], has become or at least have the will to become hegemonic, i.e., taken for granted in society to an extent that it is natural, that it goes without saying, and that criticism of the ideology is hard or even impossible to perform. Indeed, some would say: «don't you think sustainability is a good thing?» Others consider that criticism of sustainability is levelled by outsiders, outcasts, rebels that in reality isn't criticizing sustainability, but use the critique as a mean by doing what they need to do, criticising, in order to sustain their character of being an outcast, i.e., criticising sustainability is part of their sustainability as outcasts.

Maybe I am an outcast, performing this critique of sustainability. But the definition of sustainability is a rather peculiar definition for me, both in science for me as an economist, and in politics for me as a modernist. Modernism carries the conception of the economist's investment, to sacrifice today in order to reap more benefits tomorrow. The investment category and the modernist ideology says that today is probably («probably» is used in order to indicate risk) better than yesterday, and tomorrow will probably (again, due to risk) be better than today. That means that with an

investment and by following the modernist continuous improvement project, the future generation will probably – again, due to risk – get more possibilities and experience more alternatives. The modernist investment influences the coming generations through enlarging the future possibilities of the coming generation to satisfy their needs. Contrary to the modernist idea, the sustainability definition appears to imply a preservation and not an expansion. One could say that the concept of sustainability puts an end to the modern project and becomes a preservation project, that is, a conservative project, well aligned with the world view of the 7th Earl of Grantham.

Gray [14] claims that sustainability is a paradox since it is conservative against nature, but modernist towards society, since its action are focused in preserving nature by changing and controlling society. The latter is however not correct since to control society for the sake of conservation is not modernism but to have a modern view of social constructivist attitude but using it in a conservative manner.

The conservative approach is seen in the conservation idea, the demand to conserve the plants and animal species of today. It is not the species of yesterday that should be preserved, so those who claim sustainability do not demand the return of the Neanderthal, even though we, the Homo Sapiens, was probably responsible for the extinction of the Neanderthal. The goal is to preserve today's hominids, including homo sapiens. But this position of sustainability is absurd since to claim the preservation of plants and species imply the end of evolution. What is meant is probably that homo sapiens should not be as a powerful part of the evolution that we are today. Thus, it should be sustainability within the dynamic force of evolution.

But, if we are guided by a human morality claiming that we should take care of humans, and if necessary, at the expense of nature, we have to be an active actor in the evolution. With this morality, it is absurd to claim the conservation of the mosquitoes that gives malaria, or conservation of the parasite African Eye Worm, that can make people blind and increase their mortality. With this human morality it is acceptable to do what we humans have done since our first appearance, to be an active actor in the evolution by not accepting the limitation by nature but by creating instruments which we can use to manipulate nature, new plants and new types of animals

through genetic manipulation that can give us more secure food supply and to make extinct those mosquitoes and worms that kill human children.

Through this rather simple critique sustainability have been reduced from its strong form to its weak form, but still the conservative aura surrounds sustainability.

The sustainability ideology is socially conservative in that it assumes and accept both market economy and an ideal form of capitalism, disregarding for example, varieties of capitalism [18], suggesting actions of sustainability that use, and therefor accept market economy and capitalism in order to implement sustainability, but without questioning them as forces of unsustainability (Hove, 2004). It could be claimed, as indeed the old sociology professor in the introduction would claim, that market economy and especially many forms of capitalism promote class society, which is a characteristic of society that reduce the social dimension of sustainability [11]. Thus, it has been suggested that to overcome one of its conservative traits, sustainability should be transformed into «Critical sustainability» [25].

In this specific critique, I can take one example from my country. In Sweden, since the 80'ies, there has been a heated debate about the energy system, where first the ecological and now the sustainability of the energy system has been in focus. At the same time, the Swedish school system have been privatized, with private profit-seeking schools, and where the schooling itself has become a market where parents choose schools for their kids. During this process, the standard of knowledge among pupils have been significantly reduced, but in an uneven distribution, were low class pupils and immigrant pupils have significant lower knowledge than the middle-class and upper-class pupils since they, through their choice of schools, have selected schools with higher quality, especially the quality of the pupils. Thus, the marketization of the schools in Sweden has, together with some other forces, such as the housing segregation, strengthen class society and by that, reduced the lower classes opportunities to a good life. This is, in terms of sustainability, clearly not in accordance with the social dimension of sustainability since it is «<...> *compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs*». But no one, not even the Swedish Green party that stress sustainability most of them all, discuss the

schools and the schooling system in terms of sustainability. This is probably because it points towards basic organizational features of the society, which only those engaged in critical sustainability deals with.

I give another example, maybe more comedy than reality, but that put the finger on my basic critique of sustainability, that it has a conservative orientation. EU has decided that nuclear power is a sustainable source of energy production, but with the reservation if it can «safely dispose of radioactive waste». One friend of mine is working with exploring a site in Sweden as a safe place for nuclear waste. He told me that since nuclear waste must be secured under 100 000 years, they work with geological models covering 100 000 years. It implies that they consider, not one, but two inland icing periods. Obviously, they do not believe, in their models, that the climate change we now experience will heat Sweden for ever, so the swedes do not experience an inland icing period. The last inland icing in Sweden started 115 000 years ago, which were 30 000 years before humanity, i.e., Homo Sapiens, nearly got extinct, probably due to a dramatic climate change from a volcano. The last piece of this inland ice left Sweden 10 000 years ago. That was when humans started to become farmers in the Middle east, China, Peru and Mexico. Climate change appears to be a natural continuous and slow process, but could also, as the eruption of the volcano that almost made humans extinct, happens very quickly, and, as the climate change shows today, can also be very fast and influenced by one of the species on earth, Homo Sapiens.

But, is climate change, by way of heating, bad in the sense that it is «<...>*compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs?*» For some people, in some areas, it will certainly be bad and indeed, very bad for some, even destroying their possibility to live in their areas. But for me, as a Swede, living in Scania, in the south of Sweden, if climate heating implies no inland icing, it could be something good. It will imply that my house will not be crushed by the inland ice, and it will imply that my relatives, if they stay in Scania, 30 000 years from now can live and grow food in Scania, maybe enlarging their abilities to meet their own needs through giving opportunities to grow grapes and tobacco. Thus, sustainability, if it implies no climate interference, will have as a consequence the risk of inland icing of my home and that the future generations will not

experience a positive change, such as producing wine and cigars in Scania. If we succeed in fighting global heating, my relatives have to do what I have to do, to go to Italy for the warm sun.

The second critique, which I will only mention, is that the definition of sustainability contains the concept of needs, that is hard to operationalize [1]. It is hard, if possible, to imagine the needs of the future generations, thus we cannot know today what we can do today that will not influence the future generations abilities, by reducing or enlarging the future generations capacity to satisfy their needs. What we do, is assuming that the future generation will have the same needs and the same preferences as we have. This is, indeed, the view of the 7th Earl of Grantham, a conservative attitude.

The ideology of sustainability is supported by strong societal forces, that produce and reproduce its hegemonic character. The international political organization, UN, originally a peace organization, has a program for sustainability, Agenda 2030, that, for example, contains PRME, which imply that business schools and universities with programs in business studies integrate Agenda 2030 in its education. Many universities have accepted PRME and started to integrate the UN agenda in their programmes and teaching. Thus, universities are promoting the ideology of sustainability according to the political organization UN, i.e., universities are active in producing and reproducing the ideology according to UN. Today, not only the single university professors are taking a stand, but also universities as organizations. The sociology professor I mentioned in the introduction, if being alive, would envy this development, not for its content, which he would think is conservative and not progressive, but for its power to be hegemonic. The ideology of sustainability succeeded where the ideology of communism failed.

To be part of a hegemonic process, promoting a special kind of ideology, is by no means a new activity by universities. Before the scientific revolution the universities were engaged in promoting Christianity as an ideology. Indeed, sustainability and Christianity have similarities as ideologies. Both contains an overriding principle, that is self-evident, and where critics of the principle is met with, at best, exclusion, and at worst, as in medieval times, with fire. I have experienced this similarity since I have been fired

from a professor position because of me refusing to accept the teaching **for** sustainability, i.e., teaching an ideology. Today, luckily for me, universities do not put disobedient professors on a fire, but they fire them.

With this definition of sustainability, containing a conservative direction, it implies that universities that accept sustainability as a leading principle for their teaching and research direction, using the concept, with its conservative connotations, runs the risk of being an active conservative indoctrinating power in society [17]. That is the opposite of modern mission of the university, which is to be a critical agent in society, producing and disseminating scientific knowledge.

Should academics and universities be autonomous from society, or should they influence society through activism?

An academic researcher shall enjoy academic freedom, i.e., Freiheit der Wissenschaft, only limited by the professional standards and ethics. This imply that the researcher is autonomous when it concerns the choice of research question, its theories, its research object and its scientific research methods. But, at the same time, the researcher is heteronomous through being a professional academic researcher, which means to follow the professional standards, ethics and scientific methods of the academic profession.

The autonomy is needed since the independence gives opportunities to explore reality in ways never performed before, to ask questions and to present results that are not directed or bounded by political, religious or other societal forces. The heteronomy, on the other hand, consists of the need to follow accepted professional standards, thus ensuring the scientific community, but also society that the produced knowledge is scientific.

Habermas [17] made a distinction between empirical-analytical science, historical-hermeneutic science, and critically emancipatory science. In the empirical-analytical science the researcher is autonomous from the research object. In the historical-hermeneutic science the researcher interacts and in certain methods influence unintentionally the object and therefore the results. In the critically emancipatory science, the intention is to influence, thus it contains not only scientific standards but also political values that direct the researchers will to influence. Critical science is therefore putting

up one more heteronomy force that limits the researcher's autonomy not only by scientific professional standards but also directing the researcher and the research through political values. This transforms the academic researcher into a political activist researcher. The results of the activist researcher can therefore not receive the trust from society as being scientific since it is guided by a both a political and a knowledge will.

There is one condition of academic researchers that can create a «structural stress» [28] for an academic researcher since it puts the academic freedom at risk. Researchers are not only paid by universities but also often paid by foundations, corporations, organizations, and especially by the government, to produce scientific knowledge. This could question the autonomy of the academic researcher since it could influence the academic researcher to have the will to satisfy the interest of the financier. This combination of financing conditions and the condition of academic freedom constitute a «structural stress» for an academic researcher. However, an academic researcher with strong professional academic standards, stressing the autonomy of the academic freedom, working in a good university environment, i.e., at a university that is characterized by academic freedom, would not experience the structural stress.

Scientific researchers could keep autonomy but within an assignment, to create knowledge that is wanted by society. Accepting an assignment to perform research about sustainability is not, as long as it is freely accepted and also motivated by scientific reasons, a threat towards the Freiheit der Wissenschaft, especially not if the researcher, after accepting the assignment, thereafter freely, within the professional standards, select the appropriate method and publish the results, whatever they are.

The grounding question is if researcher should create knowledge about society or for society? In many cases the researcher has got the education to become a researcher by government or by private schools. Do not those financiers have the right to demand something in return, i.e., knowledge for society? In the context of academic freedom that question is given the answer that the academic researcher gives scientific knowledge as deemed by the academic freedom only limited by the professional standards. Those that claim that researchers have to give back to society by creating scientific knowledge that fulfils the interest of society have the problem of defining

who is society? What interest, of all the diverse interests existing in society, should be the guide for knowledge creation?

Could democracy, that most of us believe in, be the guide? If the parliament decide about the wanted research orientation, and we have all the reason to believe that the parliament decision is a balanced interest expression, then do we, the academics, have to accept it as a guide for our research?

This intervention in the academic freedom by the democracy exists in Sweden today.

Take a look at the Swedish Higher Education Act, section 5:

«The university must in its activities promote apartheid, which means that every present and future racial group is assured of an ethnic and racially good environment, which promotes the different races».

Should an academic researcher in Sweden accept to do research directed by the idea of apartheid, with the argument that it is the Swedish law as decided by the democratic parliament? Since universities in Sweden, to large extent are financed by taxpayers' money, their interest, as expressed by the democratic laws, should be fulfilled and therefor direct the teaching and research of the universities and their academic researchers.

Many, if not a dominating majority of the Swedish researchers would say strongly NO! and invoke the academic freedom as an argument and turning their back to the legislation.

Luckily for the dominating majority of the researchers, my citation is false. It is not correct. But unluckily, it has some truth, because the correct citation, with my English translation, is:

«In their activities, universities must promote sustainable development, which means that current and future generations are assured of a healthy and good environment, economic and social welfare and justice». (The Higher Education Act, section 5.)

If «In their activities...» is meant their education and their research, teachers have to teach in and for, not only about sustainability, and researchers have to study sustainability if they want to follow the Swedish law.

As an academic, I am not obeying the Swedish law, but the professional norms of academic freedom. Therefore, I have indeed studied sustainability

issues [26; 3; 27; 8; 5] but I did it because it is a subject existing in the environment of my subject and because it is of interest in my scientific subject. I have not studied sustainability because it is a law or that society have expectations that I perform such research.

If society, if organizations and interest groups want any research, they cannot command it, not even by law, since it goes against the basic value of a university, the academic freedom. They can, however, offer research opportunities, where autonomous academics, following the professional norm of academic freedom, evaluate the proposal and find out if it is in the interest of their subject to perform such research. Thus, academic freedom, with its *Freiheit der Wissenschaft*, the right of a researcher to freely chose object and methods of research, is a professional norm that overrides the laws of society.

Ultimately, society have to trust the academics to be «...*the impartial guardian and promoter of social critique, providing all sides and parties with the material that fundamental political critique is made of*» [28, p. 677]. Finally, I now state my position. A university and their academic researchers, in their teaching and research, could do teaching and research **about** sustainability, i.e., as a phenomenon that exists in society, and therefore could be studied, explained and understood through our scientific methods. With this position I am contrary to those claiming teaching **for** sustainability [17], demics could teach and do research **about** ideologies, but not **for** ideologies, i.e., to promote any ideology. Universities should not engage in teaching or research **for** sustainability as a must and a should, i.e., as a norm. Universities are organizations for scientific knowledge about society, not organizations that reproduces and disseminates any ideology, how good or bad it can be. From this follows almost logically that universities and academics cannot act in accordance to any other ideology than academic freedom. Thus, political activism is out of bounds for universities and academics. Then they turn into political actors and organisations, and cannot therefor be trusted as academic institutions.

In research, academics have to follow the Weberian notion that politics is about declaring goals, while action-oriented science explores the different ways and their level of efficiency in reaching those goals, without promoting any way. Academics creates scientific knowledge, while society and all its

interest groups choose knowledge that fits society and them. Of course, given the fact of Myrdal [22], it is trivial to note that science contains values, and that scientists carry values that influence them in their studies (Finseraas, Midtbøen & Thorbjørnsrud, 2022), but it is as trivial to claim that we have to be aware of these values and we have to fight as much as possible to keep values out from science, or at least, as Myrdal promoted, to make them explicit. The fact that science contains values is not an argument for flooding science with values, and the existence of values in science do not legitimize their existence.

Is my subject, business administration, free from ideological elements?

I have showed the ideological normative content of sustainability and claimed that universities and academics should stay out of ideology, as much as possible. Now I turn the attention on my own academic subject, business administration, and will show that it already contains ideological elements.

It is hard to be free from ideology in science, i.e., free from concepts and theories that contains open declared or hidden values, normative statements and/or supports one of the groups of society, typically through legitimizing them and their actions. This is especially true in the science of economics. I will in this section touch anecdotally upon some content of my subject, business administration, collected from my specific area in this subject, being accounting and finance, in order to show elements of ideology. These elements consist of the very definition of economics, some of the models of the corporation we have, the capital budgeting idea of net present value, financial accounting and, lastly, a suspicion that has been raised, that we train economists into the ideology of egoism. By this I want to show that we have already ideological material in our science, but, as I wrote in the previous section, this do not make ideology accepted, but, on the contrary, should make us even more prone to criticise our subject and to isolate as much as possible the ideological content.

Economics is the science of the production, distribution and consumption of goods and services. Very often it is added in the definition that resources are scarce, which imply that choices have to be made considering the

scarcity. Thus, economics can be regarded, to some extent, as being a science of choices under the limitation of scarce resources. Then the normative, i.e., the ideological content, enter into the science by the question: Given the scarce resources, what production, distribution and consumption produce the best outcome, the highest value? That question is often at the centre of economics, subsumed under the concept of economizing. But, both resources and especially value contains interest. For the worker, her and his body is a resource. For the employer, that hires the worker, the body is not the resource of interest, but the individual's productive capacity. Thus, there exists factory environments that destroy the body resource of the employees since the economizing behaviour of the employee do not consider the body, since that is not priced, only the service the worker can give has a price. Highest value is also even more ideological since we have to ask, who defines what the relevant value is?

In business administration as a subject, we have developed ideas of the corporation, how it is working and for what purpose. While being loaded with empirical observations, models of corporations have turned into ideal types of corporations, that slowly turns into ideologies when individuals forget that the models started their lives as ideas, with some empirical data, about the functioning of the corporation. Scientific models of corporations can therefore transform over time and turn into normative ideas of how a corporation should function.

While one can find many such models of corporations that can be turned into ideologies, i.e., claimed to be the truth and the wanted order of business, I believe the most established ones, at least in teaching, but also in many research streams, are managerialism, corporatism, shareholderism and stakeholderism.

Managerialism, i.e., when managers and their interest are governing the corporation, were claimed by Berle & Means, Burnham and Galbraith to guide the American corporations. There is indeed a difference in teaching students that managers have been found to have operational responsibility of an organization, to tell them that managers should have operational responsibility of organizations, the latter being ideological, the former empirical. The practice of our societies has been converted from a description of practise, but partly also of legislation, to become a norm of

practise, i.e., it has become praxis. It is hard to find the causal link, i.e., what came first and what influenced what. Is it this causal chain: Managerialism in practise => scientific description of managerialism in practise => legitimization of managerialism as the natural practise, i.e., praxis => norm of managerialism => reproduction of managerialism. Or is it much simpler, like this: Interaction between practise and science => the praxis of managerialism?

Corporatism, (not to be confused with corporativism) is another model by which I mean that the corporation have been found to be a self-serving organization with the goal of surviving. It can be found in the stewardship theory, where the board of directors and the TMT acts or normatively should act for the survival of the corporation as such. It can also be found in institutional theory, where institutions are directing the corporation. And it can be said to be inherent in the basic assumption of the going concern in financial accounting, thus turning into a normative statement.

Shareholder orientation, especially appearing in the subject of finance, where the shareholders are identified as the group of actors that the corporation has as a goal to support through maximization of the wealth of the shareholders. Here we teach that optimization of shareholder value should be performed, i.e., it is a goal not questioned or discussed but assumed as a natural fact in capitalism. With this optimization, the other stakeholder's interest, including nature and social peace, becomes reduced to limitations.

Stakeholder orientation, as in the stakeholder model, is when management is claimed to be an balancing entity that balance all stakeholders and their interests. In this model, sustainability enters in an interesting way since one stakeholder is the future generation. The problem with this is that the voice of the future generation cannot be heard since it does not exist.

All these perspectives are presented in good teaching and good research as different views, even as ideal types, which we can use in order to both organize data, i.e., to describe reality, and to explain reality. But a heavy yoke rest on the shoulders of us, the academics, to know these different perspectives, to consider them all and to consider them as ideal types. If we give up the diversity and focus solely on one, that we present as being The Model of the Corporation, and even worse, if we claim that the purpose

of the corporation in The Model is, should be and have to be the purpose of the corporations in reality, then we have turned ourselves into academic activists, that support and promote an ideology.

Thus, the perspectives and models as such do necessary represent ideology, but our use of them turn ideological if we convert them from being ideal types to become ontological.

In economics, or more specific, in capital budgeting, we have the idea of net present value, claiming that money, or rather that resources have higher value today than resources tomorrow. Why is that? Of course, there is risk, inflation and opportunity costs. But a family having some potatoes knows that if they can starve a little bit today and put some of the potatoes in the soil, they will eventually end up with many more potatoes in the future. Thus, the potato today has less value today, for eating, than it will have in the future, when it has become many more potatoes. The potato as such has a low value today, but as an investment, a sacrifice, it will bring a huge value tomorrow. The capital budgeting idea is the opposite, claiming that the potato has higher value today than tomorrow since its capacity to grow is devalued through discounting. This example indicates that maybe does net present value give less investments than could have been performed, if we saw the value of the future.

This tendency, to reduce the value of the future, does also imply that if we do something today that will have large costs in the future, for example large environmental costs, these large costs do not appear as large for us today since we consider them through our discounting eyeglasses, which do not enlarge the costs, but, on the contrary, the thinking of net present values reduce the costs.

So, net present value perspective tends to decrease the value of the future and increase the value of today. Thus, it appears to contain a norm, which is an ideological content. Net present value is *Carpe idem*. It is used for investment analysis, but is an idea for a hedonistic society, where tomorrow is another day. I think that we really need to consider the implications of net present value and its capacity to, maybe, hinder us from considering the future, the place where our kids and their kids will live. And then remember that in the calculus of net present value are only the priced resources.

Accounting is a subject within business administration with two orientations. One is positive accounting where we try to explain or understand why corporations report in a certain way. The larger part of the accounting subject, especially in teaching, is the normative accounting theory, telling us how economic entities should report in order to behave in accordance with an established, logical system.

This normative orientation of accounting is, overall, an ideological instrument, supporting the interest of the owner of the organization. Normative accounting can be criticized for its one-sided view, focusing on the interest of the owner of the entity, noticing the resource changes that ultimately affect the owner. As a reaction to this owner orientation, social accounting, considering the humans of the corporation, appeared and became very important, at least in Sweden, in the 70'ies. But with the increase of the market orientation in the 80'ies it was reduced to some lines in the accounting report. Today, sustainability reporting has become even more important as social reporting was. And we, the universities, have some courses in this. We have the courses because the students need to know about modern accounting reports. But also, to balance the ordinary teaching in normative accounting, i.e., to reduce the one-sidedness, the focus on the owner's interest. By this, both the teaching and the research is less one-sided, more critical, and therefore run less risk of ideology reproduction. Thus, teaching and research **about** sustainability is part of the critical university. Teaching and research **for** sustainability is, on the other hand, part of a political organisation.

A small note can be made here. We teach ROE, return on equity, since the profit of the corporation, the return, will be related to the capitalist contribution to the corporation, i.e., equity. We have formulas for calculating ROE that we spend many hours explaining, and we show, through leverage, how ROE can be increased through debt, thus promoting ideas of lending. But we do not teach ROE, return on emissions, which is to relate the return of the corporation to the nature's contribution, the sacrifice made by the nature. The silent assumption is that, in a capitalist economy, corporations exist for the sake of the capitalist, i.e., the shareholder model, where the nature is a limitation if it is represented by a price, maybe as by the costs of emission rights, otherwise it is a free resource.

Finally, some have claimed that teaching in economics and in business administration foster students to egoism, not only teach them an ideology but also to live by the ideology. The dominating paradigm of economics assume self-interest as the motivator in the economy. The dominating theory in many organizational studies is agency theory, which also assumes self-interest. It is claimed that teaching in business schools promote the ideology and the behaviour of egoism. That is probably not correct. I and my co-researcher have done one study of Swedish students in business administration, where we could not find an increase in moral orientation during the three-year program that could be interpreted as egoism (Collin & Schmidt, 2020). I and my co-researchers have done a comparative study of students in Kharkiv, Ukraine, comparing business students with students in language, where we found indications of the humanist students to have higher moral orientation towards egoism, i.e., the opposite to the hypothesis [21]. Recently I and my co-researchers gained Italian data, using the same instrument as in the published studies, that do not indicate a higher egoistic orientation as a result of education among business students compared to students from humanistic subjects [6]. While one has to be very humble when doing studies of moral orientation, the three studies indicate that it is probably not true that business programmes push students in an egoistic orientation. It could very well be the case that business programs promote some ideologies and influence students to a certain weltanschauung, i.e., a world view. But at least, there is no strong indication that the business education influences the student's moral orientation towards egoism.

With these negative results concerning the business programs to infuse ideology into students, maybe the aim of some universities, to teach not **about**, but **for** sustainability is in vain. As little as the students become prophets of egoism, they become prophets of sustainability.

With these anecdotal examples, mainly from my part of business administration, accounting and finance, it is hard to escape the impression that our subject indeed contains elements of ideology, and even more, that we have opportunities of ideology through one-sidedness and lack of critique. But this impression does not give us the right to teach and conduct studies of sustainability as an ideology. Instead, it puts even harder demand

on us to always be aware of the ideological elements and to, if it is not possible to avoid them, at least present them as ideological elements.

Has my subject, business administration, elements of sustainability?

I found in the previous section that business administration contains ideological elements. Here I will touch on the question if sustainability already is contained within the subject, especially finance and accounting, or if the subject opposes sustainability. If there are elements of sustainability concerning for example long-term considerations and resource consumption, then maybe business administration is apt for sustainability and through these elements have been dealing with sustainability before the invention of the term. There are, however, also elements that appear to be opposing the main ideas of sustainability.

In this section I will continue the anecdotal inspection of the subject by noticing reporting, the big business of sustainability, the family business survival goal, limited liability, and end with the notion of equilibrium that is dominating in economics.

Long-term considerations can be found in the business administration sub-subject of accounting. The grounding assumption of financial accounting is going concern, assuming that the economic organization have an eternal life. Since some parties, especially the one that financial accounting is created for, the owners, want to know the value created in a period, i.e., the profit defined as revenues less costs, and since there is no end for the organization, accountants need to consider accruals. By considering accruals, accountants have become experts in approximating costs, i.e., resource consumption that is not necessarily represented by an expense. One could therefore claim that that sustainability thinking is not anything new but is the very starting point of financial accounting.

However, the problem with the sustainability in financial accounting is that it concerns only specific types of resources. A resource considered and observed in financial accounting have many different dimensions, such as control, but a resource is ultimately defined with a value in monetary terms, which can be derived, direct or indirect, from a price, be it market defined or defined in other ways. Thus, a resource in financial accounting

is always valued in monetary terms and based on prices. If there is a price on a resource, it will be observed, i.e., recorded, and therefore being considered through the lenses of financial accounting. This is a feature of financial accounting independent on the financial context, be it a capitalistic context, a socialist or a planned economy context. If there is no price, the resource and its consumption will not be considered. If there are resource consumption that is for free, for example the health of the worker or air, it will not show up in the financial accounts.

This deficiency of financial accounting, and given the importance of financial accounting, has created two reactions. One is to create prices on resources, mimicking ownership, which inevitably means that state organizations create prices, which more correctly could be termed taxes on resources, or market where imaginary rights are traded, such as emission rights. The second is to create indirect prices on resources, which is when corporations experience institutional pressure, for example by consumers not buying their products or through political organizations creating public debate about resource consumption. The cost of consumption of the resources enters indirectly into the financial accounting through for example less sales of a product.

Some critics claim that lack of sustainable actions can be blamed on the profit-oriented capitalistic corporation. While it is partly true, the fact that organizations, in whatever economic system, use the Italian financial accounting system, as presented by Pacioli, makes them prone to only consider, through the financial accounting systems, resources that carry a price. Ultimately, one cannot blame capitalism but have to blame Pacioli and his successful system.

Another reaction to the deficiency is the social reporting that has complemented financial accounting with accounting for resources lacking prices. In the 70'ies there was social reporting and today we have sustainability reporting, for example the «triple bottom line» (TBL). Today, due to the institutional pressure on sustainability, this is big business, both in the economy, for example at the audit firms, but also among researchers, as all conferences and paper published concerning sustainability indicate. In the economy the attempt of sustainability reporting is criticized for

representing greenwashing, i.e., the more you report, the greener you appear. Indeed, it has been claimed to support less sustainability instead of more [20]. To that critique we can only say that Pacioli's system was not perfect at the start and has indeed developed. At least we have to acknowledge that sustainability reporting exists and has become a 'natural' part of the corporation's institutional promotion. While being not perfect and still in adolescent development, a lack of this reporting would be a perfect imperfection.

The research on sustainability reporting is also a big industry with many, many correlations studies. Probably driven by several forces, such as its importance in the economy, the fashion of sustainability, the political interest by academics in these studies and also by methodological concerns, where the rather easy data access drives the correlation studies. Sadly enough it is very uncommon to find a study that tries to correlate actual sustainability actions with sustainability reporting, probably because of methodological hardships.

Very few studies ask the question: Is sustainability a result of profit, that is, if you have profit, you can use part of the profit on sustainability actions, or does it drive profit, that is, sustainability is an element of financial success? Does a corporation first invest in sustainable actions and then receives higher profit, or are sustainable investments made out of a good profit. Or, instead of having our endless discussion on causality, looking for The Single Cause, are they simultaneous, i.e., a well-managed corporation is good in many respects, including being good in sustainability and good in producing profit?

Another interesting question is if reporting creates actions, as indeed we sometimes teach in our budget and accounting classes. Is it the case that the deficiency of the reporting system to consider sustainability issues have created a non-financial reporting that push corporations towards sustainability actions in order to avoid being accused of greenwashing, i.e., you get what you report?

Another feature of business administration is its study of family firms. They are organizations that are not operated according to the assumption of profit maximization, but according to the corporatism model, for the

survival of the firm, so it can support the family in several generations. Since a family contains adults, but also children that will become adults, the family business has to support, not only the adults and their children of today, but also the children when they have become adults in the future, and their children. This infuses the family business with a strong logic of survival. Of course, economic sustainability of an organization does not imply social and ecological sustainability actions per se, but at least, it contains sustainability in the meaning of handing over to the next generation in order to make them have, at least the same opportunities, or maybe also more opportunities than the outgoing generation.

It is worth noting that we in economics have taught the profit motive as the overarching corporate motive for more than 100 years. But the most frequent firm in capitalistic countries is the family firm, which appear to have survival and not maximum profit as the overriding motive. Strangely enough, it was first at the year 2007 the family firm were given its own performance concept in the science of business. It is termed socio-emotional wealth, and came from a study of olive-oil mills in Spain [12]. Maybe this fact indicates an ideological bias that has made the researchers in economics blind for the most frequent firms' motive.

One founding principle of the modern corporation is limited liability. It was an excellent innovation of the 1800, that made the limited liability company such a success since the corporation could attract more capital and therefore do more investments since the investor did not risk more than its investment in the corporation. But this innovation it turned debt into residual capital, since the investors only had to return to the debtholders the amount they had invested in the corporation, not the amount the corporation owed [8].

But limited liability is even worse. In the case of a corporation that has mistreated the environment and then gone bankrupt, no one can trace the investors and ask them to pay for the environmental costs. They will claim «Limited liability» and then go back to their wallet and count the money they earned as profit when they polluted the environment. Thus, limited liability is not only limited liability towards the debtholders, but also to nature and society. Limited liability is organized and legitimate irresponsibility.

While there are some elements in the subject of business administration that do not appear to fit well with sustainability, there is one that fits very well, that of equilibrium. Economics have a well-developed attraction to the idea of equilibrium. It exists in the double-entry Italian book keeping, where debit and credit balance. It exists in the price, where a price is established when demand and supply reach each other. And it is well established today as ecological equilibrium in sustainability.

But, while equilibrium can appear to be dynamic, it is the opposite. The road to equilibrium is the dynamic part, while the balance is the static, frozen moment of no change. Thus, it appears that the conservative attitude that I found in sustainability is also present in the strong sustainability idea of economics, the equilibrium.

Why do we not change focus, from the balancing point of the equilibrium to the movement from or to the balancing point? We could instead focus on adaptability, i.e., to be capable to change, to adapt if something is happening, and when nothing is happening, we create an action. We could even go one step further and stress changeability, i.e., to be able to induce change among adaptive entities. Herakleitos said, *Panta Rei*, which means that nothing is as it was, thus, what exists is change, not same stable state, like equilibrium. Maybe equilibrium, at least concerning humans' affairs, is just another word for the inertia of institutions?

This sketchy and anecdotal mentioning of some examples from my subject, business administration, indicate that my subject has some notions that is of value for studies of sustainability, but that, at present, it is not yet well suited for considering sustainability. The reason is probably that the subject has been developed in describing the present practise, which is its academic duty, and then, maybe without intent, been promoting what they found, i.e., praxis. With the conclusion from the preceding part, adding this parts anecdotes, it is hard to avoid the conclusion that business administration has been part of legitimizing and promoting the existing way of doing business, i.e., it has not avoided wholeheartedly to be a reproductive actor of the ideology of society. In this sense, to teach for sustainability would not break the tradition. It would only purify and drag the tradition to its logical end point, where education and research are directly and admittedly subject to an ideology.

A concluding call for academic professionalism supporting society

I have found that sustainability is a conservative ideology that could be taught **about** but not **for** at universities and be studied by autonomous professional academic researcher for the sake of knowledge, not for the sake of social change. I found that my subject, business administration, especially accounting and finance, is not free from ideological elements and I found the subject to contain ideas of sustainability or ideas that could be used in studies and teaching about sustainability, but also ideas that are contrary to sustainability. I have stressed that bad practise does not motivate or legitimate continuation of bad practise. Bad practise should push us to improve our practise through realizing our professional duty, to perform and teach scientific knowledge.

In this concluding section I make a call for academics at universities and for universities to implement and safeguard academic freedom, implying among other things, no ideology directed research or teaching, but solely directed towards creating and disseminating scientific knowledge.

Our duty is to produce scientific knowledge, and to supply it to the scientific community in order to build knowledge, and to supply it to society, thereby helping society to reflect on possible actions. An academic has therefore an professional and egalitarian approach and refutes elite and power approaches.

1. We produce scientific knowledge through following the principle of academic freedom only limited by our professional standards, i.e., we have a professional approach

2. We give our knowledge to everyone so it can be used by everyone, i.e., we have an egalitarian approach.

3. We do not support our own individual political views through activism i.e., we do not have an elite approach.

4. We do not support specific groups or organizations, i.e., we do not have a power approach, even if the power approach exists due to interest groups being powerful to attracting research through funding

We recognize our subjectivity and struggle with it, through reflection, self-criticism and debate, accepting that it can influence the choice of research subject, but we do not allow it to influence our method or our

presentation of the results, where our eternal strive is for objectivity and autonomy, limited only by our professional standards.

Sustainability is a phenomenon existing today, which motivate us to study it, as we study all other existing social phenomena's of today. Its existence in society is a research possibility, but not a necessity to study and no-one, not the King, not the Parliament, not the Rector, not them together can demand us to study or teach it.

To let sustainability become a necessity to teach and to study, as in UN's PRME initiative, is a violation of academic freedom, and to promote sustainability as an academic person, in teaching, research and in societal action is to become an ideological conservative actor in society. Both are opposing the very essence of scientific work, to be a critical force in society.

But, as indicated anecdotally here, we in the subject of business administration do perform ideological actions when we let the critical essence of science diminish through one-sidedness in perspectives and through not critically evaluating our concepts. But, as also anecdotally indicated here, there are elements of sustainability existing inherent in the subject of business administration.

Thus, business administration can and do contribute to the scientific exploration of sustainability, as long as we safeguard ourselves from ideology and activism.

The conservative character of sustainability is not damaging in a knowledge sense since we, as critical academics, teach **about** sustainability. It becomes damaging if we teach **for** sustainability, since it implies that the university support conservative ideologies.

The only ideology academics should support is the one that carries the norm of free thinking and free expression: «*Academic duty and the needs of the decent society coincide in suggesting that academic thought should remain fundamentally critical of all practices, those of activists, those of rulers, and any others*» [28]. Our aim is to produce scientific knowledge, for society to enjoy and use.

References

1. Beckerman, W. (1994). Sustainable development: Is it a useful concept? *Environmental Values*, 3 (3), pp. 191–209.

2. Bonevac, D. (2010). Is sustainability sustainable? *Academic Questions*, 23, pp. 84–101.
3. Broberg, P., Tagesson, T. and Collin, S-O, (2010). What explains variation in voluntary disclosure? A study of the annual reports of corporations listed on the Stockholm Stock Exchange. *Journal of Management & Governance*, 14, pp. 351–377.
4. Brundtland, G.H. (1987). *Our Common Future*. Geneva, *UN-Document A/42/427*.
5. Collin, S.-O. Y. (2018). Sustainable and responsible Academic Freedom. In: *Educational risks: essence and approaches to solution*. Kharkiv.
6. Collin, S-O, Liberatore, A. and Vagnoni, E. Does a university education influence students' moral orientation? A survey of Italian business students. *International Journal of Pluralism and Economics Education*.
7. Collin, S.-O., Y., Schmidt, M. (2020). The university influence on moral orientation of Swedish accounting students: Selection and education. *Issues in Educational research*, 30 (1), pp. 35–37.
8. Collin, S.-O. (1996). Bad Losers - An Investigation of the Morality of the Limited Liability of the Shareholders in a Joint Stock Company. *Journal of Economic Issues*, 30 (1), pp. 283–289.
9. Fokkema, J.T.F., Jansen, L. and Mulder, K.F. (2005). Sustainability: necessity for a prosperous society. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 6 (3), pp. 219–228.
10. Finseraas, H., Midtbøen, A. H. and Thorbjørnsrud, K. (2022). Ideological biases in research evaluations? The case of research on majority-minority relations. *Scandinavian Political Studies*, 45 (3), pp. 370–381.
11. Fuchs, C. (2017). Critical social theory and sustainable development: The role of class, capitalism and domination in a dialectical analysis of un/sustainability. *Sustainable development*, 25 (5), pp. 443–458.
12. Gomez-Mejia, L. R., Takacs, K. H., Nunez-Nickel, M. and Jacobson, K. J. L. (2007). Socioemotional wealth and business risks in family-controlled firms: Evidence from Spanish olive oil mills. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 52, pp. 106–137.
13. Gramsci, A. (1971). *Selections from the Prison Notebooks of Antonio Gramsci*. New York: International Publishers.
14. Gray, R. (2010). Is accounting for sustainability actually accounting for sustainability...and how would we know? An exploration of narratives of organisations and the planet. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 35 (1), pp. 47–62.

15. Habermas, J. (1972) *Knowledge and human interest*. Sec. ed. London: Heinemann.
16. Hove, H. (2004). Critiquing Sustainable Development: A Meaningful Way of Mediating the Development Impasse? *Undercurrent*, 1 (1), pp. 48–54.
17. Kearins, K., Springett, D. (2003). Educating for sustainability: Developing critical skills. *Journal of Management Education*, 27 (2), pp. 188–204.
18. Loewen, B. (2022). Revitalizing varieties of capitalism for sustainability transitions research. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 162 (July), pp. 1–12.
19. Loring, P. A. (2020). Threshold concepts and sustainability: features of a contested paradigm. *Facets*, 5 (1), pp. 182–199.
20. Milne, M. J., Gray, R (2013). W(h)ither Ecology? The Triple Bottom Line, the Global Reporting Initiative, and Corporate Sustainability Reporting. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 118 (1), pp. 13–29.
21. Mykolenko, O., Collin, S.-O-, Strokovych, A. and Basmanova, O. (2020). The impact of academic studies on ethical ideology of Ukrainian students. *Journal of East European Management Studies*, 25 (2), pp. 360–383.
22. Myrdal, G. (1969). *Objectivity in Social Research*. London: Gerald Duckworth.
23. Olawumi, T. O., Chan, D. W. M. (2018). A scientometric review of global research on sustainability and sustainable development. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 183, pp. 231–250.
24. Purvis, B., Mao, Y. and Robinson, D. (2019). Three pillars of sustainability: in search of conceptual origins. *Sustainability Science*, 14, pp. 681–695.
25. Rose, J., Cachelin, A. (2018). Critical sustainability: incorporating critical theories into contested sustainabilities. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*, 8 (1), pp. 518–525.
26. Tagesson, T., Collin, S.-O. (2016). Corporate governance influencing compliance with the Swedish code of Corporate Governance. *International Journal of Disclosure and Governance*, 13 (3), pp. 262–277.
27. Tagesson, T., Blank, V., Broberg, P. and Collin, S-O. (2009). What explains the extent and content of social and environmental disclosures on corporate websites: a study of social and environmental reporting in Swedish listed corporations. *Corporate Social Responsibility & Environmental Management*, 16 (6), pp. 352–364.
28. Wissenburg, M. (2013). Political appeasement and academic critique: The case of environmentalism. *Philosophy and Social Criticism*, 39 (7), pp. 675–691.